

Figure S1: Morphospace occupied by *Teretrurus* species plotted from the second and third Principal Components (PC2 and PC3). A – PCA plot of the raw head measurements, B – PCA plot after size correction using the residuals from a least-square regression with SVL, C – PCA plot after size correction using Thorpe's allometric equation.